

Artifact documentation of paper entitled: Conditional Encryption with Applications to Secure Personalized Password Typo Correction

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1 Artifact Appendix

The Artifact Appendix is meant to summarize the purpose, availability, content, dependencies, and execution of the artifacts that support your paper. It should include a clear description of your artifacts' hardware, software, and configuration requirements. If your artifacts have received the Artifacts Evaluated-Functional, Artifacts Evaluated-Reusable, or Results Reproduced badge, this appendix should summarize the relevant major claims made by your paper and provide instructions for validating each claim through the use of your artifacts. Linking the claims of your paper to the artifacts allows a reader of your paper to more easily try to reproduce your paper's results.

Please fill in all the mandatory sections, keeping their titles and organization but removing the current illustrative content, and remove the optional sections that do not apply to your artifacts.

1.1 Abstract

[Mandatory] In this artifact, we describe the procedure for installing and implementing our proposed conditional encryption scheme, as well as the conditional TypTop (CondTypTop) system. The artifact is divided into two main sections: one focused on conditional encryption, and the other on CondTypTop, which is the TypTop system implemented using conditional encryption as its core building block. For each section, we provide detailed steps for installing, compiling the C++ implementation, and running basic functionality tests. Additionally, we include instructions for evaluating the performance of each part—conditional encryption and CondTypTop—by reproducing the results presented in Figure 1 and the data shown in Table 1 and Table 2. We provide a link to the detailed README.md file (<https://zenodo.org/api/records/13744111/draft/files/README.md/content>), which explains how to install the artifact, run basic tests, and evaluate performance. To simplify the

artifact review process, we have included several “*.sh” scripts that can be executed to generate the desired outputs by calling the functions contained in the compiled c++ codes. In the README.md file, we describe the expected output for each test case, which can be verified by running the provided scripts. Additionally, we offer instructions on how to obtain different results by executing the scripts with various arguments.

1.2 Description & Requirements

The experiments in this artifact were conducted on a Lenovo ThinkStation S30 with a 2.9 GHz 8-core Intel[®] Xeon[®] E5-26900x 16 CPU processor (16 cores) and 28 GiB of DDR4 RAM memory, and 1.0 TB disk. The system runs on Ubuntu 24.04 LTS with GNOME version 46 and uses the Wayland windowing system. The kernel version is Linux 6.8.0-41-generic. For those wishing to recreate the experimental environment, the minimum hardware requirements are a (optionally multi-core) processor and 16 GiB of RAM. The software requirements include a 64-bit Linux distribution, preferably Ubuntu 20.04 LTS or later, with support for GNOME and Wayland, as well as the following development tools:

- C++ compiler (g++)
- CMake (version 3.18 or later)
- Make (for compiling and building)

All scripts in the artifact rely on a Linux-based environment with access to these tools.

Benchmarks included in the artifact, executed via provided shell scripts, assess both performance and correctness. Detailed instructions for compiling the C++ code and running the performance tests are included in the README.md file. (.zip of the whole project is available at Zenodo website with its corresponding DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13744111>)

[Mandatory] The artifact is organized into several key directories and files, as can be seen in the directory of the downloaded files from Zenodo. Here is a general road map to help navigate through them:

- **README.md:** This file provides a detailed description of how to install, compile, and run the various components of the project. It also includes instructions for running tests and performance evaluations. Start here for setup instructions and usage information. This file also provide some example test case and its corresponding output.
- **src:** This directory contains the core source code, including the implementations of the cryptographic functions and conditional encryption schemes discussed in the paper. Specifically, it includes:
 - Cryptowrapper functions.

- Paillier wrapper functions.
- Conditional encryption
- Implementations for various predicates such as Hamming distance, Edit distance, CAPSLOCK_ON and OR_of_CAPSLOCK_EditDist1_HamDist2 (Typo predicate).
- **test:** This directory includes the test files and datasets used for evaluating the performance of our suggested conditional encryption schemes. The PWDVsTypoDataSet is particularly important, as it contains the random input data (pair of PWD and their typos collected from Chaterjee data set and filtered under different limitation like PWD size, hamming and edit distance, etc) fed into the conditional encryption algorithms during testing.
- **CMakeLists.txt:** This file handles the configuration of the project and facilitates the build process. It copies necessary scripts, such as TestScript.sh, to the build/test directory. This script is used to run the compiled test binaries and is critical for generating data for performance evaluations and experiments (e.g., plotting results for Figure 1.a).
- **GeneratePlotsPdfs:** This directory contains the necessary scripts and tools for plotting the results of the experiments. The CMakeLists.txt file copies this directory to the test directory, where it reads the generated “*.dat” files to produce PDF output of the experiment results. For this part, we assume that the the machine include Latex compiling software like pdflatex.
- **Third-party Libraries:**
 - argon2/phcargon2: This folder contains the implementation of Argon2, a memory-hard function used in the project
 - paillier: This directory includes the Paillier cryptosystem, which is used in various parts of the project.
 - cryptopp-cmake: is the directory which is used by our CmakeLists.txt file to install the cryptopp library.
- **Other Scripts:**
 - TestScript.sh: A key script for running customized test cases and generating experimental data.
 - FixingTestInstallCryptoPP.sh: A helper script to fix installation issues related to the Crypto++ library, which might be used in the project.

This structure is designed to keep the project modular and organized, with clear separation between the core source code, tests, and third-party dependencies.

1.2.1 Security, privacy, and ethical concerns

[Mandatory]

Root Access Requirement: Installing CondTypTop may require root access to the machine. This is because the installation process can involve modifying the Pluggable Authentication Module (PAM) on the system. Modifying PAM can affect how authentication is handled at the system level, which could potentially disrupt login processes if not done correctly. Users should ensure they have proper system backups before proceeding with the installation of CondTypTop, particularly on production machines.

Since CondTypTop modifies the PAM configuration, there is a risk of misconfiguration, which could lock users out of their systems or interfere with other authentication mechanisms. It is essential to follow the installation instructions carefully and, if possible, test the changes in a non-production environment.

No Data Privacy Risks and Destructive Actions: There are no privacy risks associated with the installation of the *conditional encryption* component. The encryption schemes operate locally, and there is no transmission of sensitive data to external sources. The encryption algorithms themselves are designed to enhance security rather than pose any threats to data privacy. The execution of the conditional encryption algorithms does not involve any destructive steps, nor does it disable any security mechanisms that could expose the machine to risks. All computations are local, and no external communication is involved, minimizing security concerns.

In summary, while CondTypTop requires caution due to potential system-level modifications, the conditional encryption component poses no significant security or privacy risks. Users should ensure they understand the changes being made to their authentication modules and test carefully before applying to critical systems.

1.2.2 How to access

[Mandatory]

The artifact-related data are publicly available on Zenodo with the DOI link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13744111>.

1.2.3 Hardware dependencies

[Mandatory] None.

1.2.4 Software dependencies

[Mandatory] The system used for this artifact runs on Ubuntu 24.04 LTS with GNOME version 46 and the Wayland windowing system. The kernel version is Linux 6.8.0-41-generic. To compile the project from source, the following software packages and dependencies are required:

- CMake (version 3.6 or later)

- protobuf: Install using `sudo apt install protobuf-compiler`
- PAM development library: Install using `sudo apt-get install libpam0g-dev`
- cURL: Install using `sudo apt install libcurl4-openssl-dev`
- Catch2: Clone the repository and build it manually
- **cryptopp**, **zxcvbn**, and **plog**: These libraries are included in the repository and will build automatically
- Argon2: The source for Argon2 memory-hard functions is included in the repository, but it requires manual building.

No proprietary software is required, and all necessary open-source dependencies can either be installed via package managers or are included in the repository.

1.2.5 Benchmarks

[Mandatory]

We use Chatterjee’s typo correction study dataset, which is publicly available at <https://pages.cs.wisc.edu/~chatterjee/projects/pwtypos.html>. Specifically, we utilized the **MTurk15-General-typing.json.bz2** dataset. From this dataset, we generated various subsets by applying specific conditions, such as filtering passwords based on lengths (less than 8, 16, 32, 64, and 128 characters) and evaluating whether the Hamming distance at most T (for $T = 1, 2, 3, 4$) holds. These extracted datasets were used for testing our conditional encryption algorithms in both basic functionality tests and performance evaluation experiments.

We should highlight that use these data sets for basic functionality test and evaluation of CondTypTop system as well.

1.3 Set Up

To set up the environment for using our artifacts, you can begin by cloning the artifact repository using standard Git commands. After cloning, execute a series of basic commands to install the necessary dependencies and compile the conditional encryption schemes and the CondTypTop system. A detailed description of these steps, including the exact commands for installation, compilation, and testing, can be found in the README.md file within the repository. This process ensures that both the encryption schemes and the CondTypTop system are correctly installed and configured for use.

1.3.1 Installation-Conditional Encryption

[Mandatory]

In what follows we mention the dependencies and the way to install and compile each project on your local machine.

Dependencies To compile the project from source, you will need the following:

- `cmake >= 3.18`
- `protobuf` source (in debian use `sudo apt install protobuf-compiler`)
- `pam-dev` (in debian use `sudo apt-get install libpam0g-dev`)
- `cURL` (in debian use `sudo apt install libcurl4-openssl-dev`) `catch2` source (to install, clone the repository and build)
- `cryptopp`, `zxcvbn` and `plog` (inside the repository, will automatically build)
- `Argon2` memory hard functions Source (inside the repository, requires manually building)

Building the Project

Clone the repository

```
$ git clone https://github.com/mhassanameri/CondEncCCS24
Artifact.git
$ cd CondEncCCS24Artifact
```

Here, for the aim of Artifact evaluation, you can download the zip file of our project form Zenodo link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13744111>

Build the Argon2 libraries

```
$ cd argon2/phcargon2
$ make
$ cd ../../
```

Create a build directory and build the program

```
$ mkdir build && cd build
$ cmake ../
$ make
```

If the `make` command fails with errors related to `g_argvPathHint`, run the following script in the build directory, and then rerun `make`:

```
$ ../FixingTestInstallCryptoPP.sh
$ make
```

Finally, to verify that the implementations of all Conditional Encryption schemes (associated with the predicates: Hamming Distance at most T, Edit Distance at most one, CAPSLOCK_ON, and OR_of_CAPSLOCK_HamDist2_EditDist1) are working correctly, run:

```
$ ./test/tests
```

The last execution runs all the test cases defined in the artifact. However, for more customized tests, such as basic tests for a specific predicate, you can use the scripts provided in the repository (which will be automatically copied to the build/test sub directory). Detailed instructions for running these basic tests are available in the "Basic Test" section of the documentation. These tests allow for focused evaluation of individual predicates, such as Hamming Distance, Edit Distance, and others, to verify their functionality in isolation.

1.3.2 Installation-CondTypTop

1.3.3 Basic test for Conditional Encryption

[Mandatory] Instructions for Running a Simple Functionality Test

- (1) Navigate to the Build Directory: Open a terminal and change to the directory where the build artifacts are located. This directory should contain the `TestScript.sh` file.

```
$ cd CondEncCCS24Artifact/build/test
```

- (2) Check the Script: Open `TestScript.sh` in a text editor to review its contents. Read through the instructions and comments inside the script. This will help you understand what the script does and if any modifications are needed to initiate the desired test before executing the following command

```
$ ./TestScript.sh
```

- (3) If the script requires modifications (e.g., setting input parameters, the number of test cases, target predicates, etc.), make the necessary changes and save the file after editing.
- (4) Ensure that `TestScript.sh` is executable by running

```
$ chmod +x TestScript.sh
```

This step may be optional as we already handled it with the `CMakeLists.txt` and you can run it just in case the script is not executing after modification.

- (5) Run the script: Now the script is ready to be executed to run our desired test case by the following command

```
$ ./TestScript.sh
```

- (6) Verify the output: As the final step, you need to verify the generated output. After running the script, check the output in the terminal. The expected successful output should indicate that all required software components are correctly installed and functioning as intended. This might include messages confirming successful execution of commands or proper setup.

After `./TestScript.sh`, (depending on the `TestScript.sh`) couple of `.dat` file are generated. To visualize the `.dat` files, there are couple of `.py` scripts which generates the output. For example for plotting Figure 1a we can run:

```
$ python3 ./PlotFigure.py Figure1a
```

Or Table 1 (CondEnc message len =32)

```
$ ./TestScriptMakingTable1data.sh
```

```
$ python3 ./PdfGenTable1.py
```

Or for CondTypTop (Table 2)

```
$ ./TestScript.sh
```

```
$ python3 ./PlotFigureCondTypTop.py
```

1.3.4 Basic test for CondTypTop

The second Part of our project is implementing TypTop with Conditional Encryption. The set up is similar and for the basic test the detailed description is available at the README.md file: <https://zenodo.org/api/records/13744111/draft/files/README.md/content>